

MARKET EFFICIENCY DYNAMICS: THE MODERN FOOTBALL TRANSFER MARKET AS A MICROCOSM TO REFLECT THE BROADER SOCIAL CONDITION

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the validity of the Efficient Market Hypothesis (EMH) by using the football transfer market as a proxy. I assess the underlying assumptions of EMH by exploring both traditional arguments and recent developments in behavioural finance. Recognising the importance of socially oriented views, I challenge the long-held assumptions of rationality, its implications, and efficient information incorporation. My methodology employs econometric analysis within this isolated sporting environment, marginalising extraneous factors for clearer insights. By applying a comprehensive two-model approach, I analyse human behavioural patterns in the transfer market and extrapolate these findings to the financial market, as the underlying agents – humans – are identical, albeit in a more emotionally hyperbolic environment. This allows evaluation of the realism of EMH assumptions. My analysis reveals that while EMH offers simplicity, it lacks a representative foundation in this market. I find significant deviations from EMH, driven by identifiable factors including player performance metrics (such as historical peak value and game involvement reflected through PCA-derived skills), structural market features leading to phenomena like the “English tax” premium, and behavioural elements captured through media sentiment and information leakage dynamics. These factors introduce biases and information asymmetries, yielding sub-optimal market efficiency as defined by EMH and demonstrating that asset valuation is influenced by a complex interplay of fundamental, structural, and behavioural drivers, not just purely informational ones.

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Abbreviations	Full Term
AMH	Adaptive Markets Hypothesis
ACF	Autocorrelation Function
AIC	Akaike Information Criterion
BIC	Bayesian Information Criterion
EDA	Exploratory Data Analysis
EMH	Efficient Market Hypothesis
ESG	Environmental, Social, and Governance
FFP	Financial Fair Play
FMH	Fractal Market Hypothesis
GBR	Gradient Boosting Regression
MAE	Mean Absolute Error
MLR	Multi-Linear Regression
MSE	Mean Squared Error
NTA	Noise Trader Approach
OLS	Ordinary Least Squares
PACF	Partial Autocorrelation Function
PCA	Principal Component Analysis
RWH	Random Walk Hypothesis
RMSE	Root Mean Squared Error
R^2	Coefficient of Determination
SEC	U.S. Securities and Exchange Commission
UEFA	Union of European Football Associations

1. Introduction

The dynamics of modern economic systems are often characterised by the efficient allocation of resources, where markets play a pivotal role in this allocation process. One of the central and enduring topics in economics is the concept of market efficiency, a cornerstone of which is the EMH. This theory refers to the extent to which information is incorporated into asset prices within the financial markets, where asset prices “fully reflect” information (Fama, 1970).

The concept of the EMH has undergone extensive examination, debate, and scrutiny within the field of economics due to its profound implications for investor decision-making, and the mechanisms of financial and economic systems. These implications are far-reaching, hinged on simplified assumptions about human behaviour, the primary drivers of financial markets.

This paper seeks to provide a meaningful commentary on the theory’s general applicability by proxy of behavioural pattern analysis, assessing the underlying assumptions of EMH, in an isolated market environment – the modern football transfer market; understanding the dynamics of market efficiency in this unique setting enables an examination of the practical relevance of EMH by scrutinising a narrower context, limiting the influence of extraneous factors such as market shocks and geopolitics which may skew results. Despite some clear disparities, many academics draw close similarities between the two markets, beginning with the fundamental underlying mechanism, supply and demand (Morrow, 1999), ranging to similar reactions to information dissemination (Szymanski, 2010), thereby providing a robust basis for using the football transfer markets as a proxy for analysis. I aim to explore the prevalence of behavioural factors in human decision-making, supporting these claims with econometric analysis to empirically evaluate the significance of the observations.

My research contributes to existing literature by uniquely applying advanced machine learning techniques, particularly Gradient Boosting Regression (GBR), to test EMH assumptions. Employing GBR represents an innovative methodological contribution, as this technique, which captures complex nonlinear relationships more effectively than traditional econometric methods alone, remains underexplored in market efficiency studies.

In summary, this paper examines EMH implications in the football transfer market, challenging its assumptions by axiom of behavioural analysis and machine learning. Section 2 introduces the market context; section 3 discusses pivotal EMH studies and synergies with football market literature; section 4 analyses modelling methodologies, emphasising Econometric and Machine Learning approaches. Section 5 discusses behavioural insights in market efficiency theories; and Section 6 concludes with reflections and future research directions, offering insights applicable across disciplines.

2. Background

Football, also known as soccer, involves two teams of eleven players each aiming to out-score the other, with only the goalkeeper allowed to handle the ball in a designated area.

Matches are split into two 45-minute halves, with league points awarded as follows: three for a win, one for a draw, and none for a loss. League teams play each other twice a year. These points determine league standings, affecting promotions and relegations. The top clubs in the elite 5 leagues, will qualify for international competitions like the UEFA Champions League, which offers substantial prestige and financial benefits. Domestic cups, while prestigious, generally do not impact league standings but can lead to European competition entries.

The transfer market is vital for clubs to strengthen their squads and manage finances, operating during the summer and winter. This market exemplifies complex economic principles such as supply and demand, valuation based on human capital, and strategic

financial investment. Clubs and analysts use detailed data analysis and econometric models to guide transactions, evaluating player value, and market dynamics.

3. Literature Review

Since its inception, the EMH has been both foundational and controversial. While early empirical studies supported the hypothesis, suggesting long-term market efficiency, subsequent research revealed persistent anomalies and inefficiencies. Over time, the rigid assumptions of EMH have been increasingly challenged by behavioural finance, which incorporates psychological factors to explain market behaviour. This literature review traces the development of these competing perspectives, highlighting how empirical evidence has evolved and emphasising the growing importance of behavioural finance as a dynamic framework. By examining key studies and their findings, this review aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the shifting landscape of market efficiency and the implications for financial theory and practice.

3.1 The Efficient Market Hypothesis Discussion

The EMH posits that asset prices incorporate all available information, rendering it exceedingly difficult for investors to achieve consistent excess returns (Malkiel, 2003). EMH is often categorised into weak, semi-strong, and strong forms, each reflecting varying levels of informational efficiency (Fama, 1991). Although this framework underpins many areas of finance, such as derivative valuation, passive investing strategies, and capital asset pricing, its validity has long been debated, particularly in light of behavioural finance developments.

Empirical research suggests that arbitrage can eventually eliminate many pricing anomalies. For example, Schwert (2003) observed that once anomalies become well-known, they often dissipate, and more recent evidence (Griffin, Kelly and Shams, 2020); Von Beschwitz, Lunghi and Schmidt, 2022) shows arbitrageurs actively correct mispricings, reinforcing long-term efficiency. However, a substantial body of research from behavioural finance challenges EMH's assumption of full rationality. Studies by

Kahneman and Tversky (1979) and Shiller (2003), among others, demonstrate that investor sentiment, overconfidence, and herd behaviour can lead to systematic pricing errors and anomalous patterns, contradicting the purely information-driven view of EMH. The Adaptive Markets Hypothesis (AMH) (Lo, 2004) further suggests that markets evolve over time as participants adapt, rather than being statically efficient.

Recent advancements in machine learning and data analytics have also exposed subtle inefficiencies that were undetectable by traditional models (Barbopoulos et al., 2021); (Gu, Kelly and Xiu, 2020). This suggests that EMH, while foundational, is not universally applicable across all market conditions and asset classes. As Grossman and Stiglitz (1980) argue, markets cannot be perfectly informationally efficient because if they were, there would be no incentive for informed traders and therefore some information-based inefficiencies must persist. In niche markets like football transfers, these inefficiencies may be even more pronounced. By examining these deviations in an isolated context, this dissertation explores whether the assumptions of EMH hold under distinct market dynamics and behavioural biases.

3.2 Likening the Financial and Football Transfer Markets

Exploring alternative methods using isolated markets as proxies offers a nuanced approach to understanding market dynamics. The academic literature reflects a bidirectional trend between financial and football transfer markets, where behaviours in one market are used to analyse and support findings in the other. This cross-pollination highlights the similarities between the two markets, particularly in facilitating transactions and redistributing assets.

Both the financial markets and football transfer markets share several core similarities. For example, the football transfer system, involving player movements between clubs through financial negotiations, mirrors the financial market's function of enabling trade and investment (Demazière and Jouvenet, 2013). Both markets rely on efficient transactions to determine the growth and competitiveness of the entities involved, whether they are football clubs or companies.

Fűrész and Rappai (2022), in their study “Information leakage in the football transfer market”, explore the parallels between football and financial markets through the lens of information leakage. Their findings show how premature leaks about player transfers can impact football club stock prices similarly to insider information in financial markets. This evidence of market sensitivity to non-public information challenges the EMH, which asserts that all available information is already reflected in market prices.

Fűrész’s evidence of market sensitivity to non-public information aligns with studies by Stadtmann (2006) and Palomino, Renneboog and Zhang (2009). The latter also explore how events in the football industry (like player transfers) influence stock valuations, akin to how corporate events (mergers, acquisitions) move stock prices in traditional markets. Bryson et al. (2013) show that clubs’ spending on players (in this case, paying a premium for scarce left-footed talent) reflects strategic considerations akin to investment decisions. This further blurs the line between transfer market behaviour and financial market behaviour.

Despite the similarities, significant disparities exist between financial markets and the football transfer market. One of the primary differences lies in regulatory constraints. In the football transfer market, strict regulations imposed by governing bodies like FIFA and UEFA aim to maintain competitive balance and prevent financial distortions caused by the influx of external financial power. These regulations include Financial Fair Play (FFP) rules, which limit the amount of money clubs can spend relative to their revenue, thereby enforcing financial discipline and sustainability (Müller, Lammert and Hovemann, 2012). This regulatory framework contrasts sharply with financial markets, where regulatory bodies like the U.S. Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) enforce laws to ensure transparency and prevent fraud, without imposing stringent spending limits on companies.

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The nature of assets being traded also distinguishes these markets. In financial markets, assets such as stocks, bonds, and derivatives are primarily financial instruments with values derived from underlying economic activities (Fabozzi, Modigliani and Jones,

2013). Conversely, the football transfer market deals with human assets (players) whose value is influenced not only by their performance but also by their marketability, physical condition, and personal ambitions (Rohde and Breuer, 2016). This human element introduces a level of unpredictability and emotional investment not present in traditional financial markets.

Market liquidity is another key difference. Financial markets typically exhibit high liquidity, allowing assets to be easily bought and sold without significant price changes (Harris, 2003). In contrast, the football transfer market is characterised by lower liquidity, with transfers occurring within specific windows and often involving lengthy negotiations (Frick, 2007). This seasonal nature of transfers requires clubs to make strategic decisions within limited timeframes, impacting market dynamics differently from the continuous trading environment of financial markets (Dobson and Goddard, 2011).

Market participants in these two markets also differ in their primary objectives and risk profiles. Investors in financial markets are often driven by profit maximisation and portfolio diversification (Markowitz, 1952). In contrast, football clubs pursue a variety of objectives, including sporting success, brand development, and community engagement, which may not always align with purely financial goals (Garcia-del-Barro and Szymanski, 2006). This divergence in objectives can lead to different decision-making processes and risk appetites, influencing market behaviour and outcomes (KPMG, 2016).

Moreover, the presence of emotional and cultural factors in the football transfer market adds complexity. Fan sentiment and media influence can significantly impact transfer decisions and player valuations, creating a market dynamic that intertwines economic factors with social and cultural elements (Dolles and Söderman, 2013). Media sentiment can dominate valuations, a phenomenon paralleling how media news drives stock market sentiment (Tetlock, 2007). Financial markets are theoretically driven by economic fundamentals and rational analysis, but investor sentiment undeniably plays a role (Shleifer, 2000).

Lastly, while both markets are subject to economic cycles, their sensitivities to macroeconomic factors can differ. The financial market's performance is closely tied to global economic conditions, interest rates, and geopolitical events (Mankiw, 2014). In contrast, the football transfer market, though affected by broader economic trends, also responds to unique factors such as tournament results, player performances, and changes in club ownership (Dobson and Goddard, 2011). For instance, Millward (2017) highlights how the ground-breaking £304 million BSkyB deal in 1992 radically increased broadcast revenues and restructured club finances in the Premier League, thereby creating a financial environment that contributed to increasing transfer fees. This dual influence of macroeconomic trends and sector-specific shocks can result in different patterns of volatility and stability between the two markets.

In summary, while there are undeniable differences between financial markets and the football transfer market such as regulatory constraints, the nature of assets, liquidity, participant objectives, and the influence of emotional and cultural factors, the similarities are significant enough to warrant comparative analysis. Both markets facilitate transactions and redistribute assets, are influenced by information flows, and exhibit strategic behaviours driven by expectations and market dynamics.

The football transfer market is a unique and valuable proxy for analysis. According to Walters and Hamil (2013), financial regulation in English football aims to limit distortions from external money. The market's controlled environment and seasonal transfer periods enable a clearer assessment of EMH assumptions. Rather than being flaws, these structural distinctions help isolate key factors.

A comparative approach not only broadens the scope of financial analysis but also provides a more holistic view of market behaviours. By examining the football transfer market's unique interplay of economic and non-economic factors, the EMH's core tenets can be tested by exploring human behaviour in a distinct context. Such an innovative method could yield insights that traditional financial market analyses might miss, enhancing our understanding of market efficiency and investor psychology.

Therefore, I find it appropriate to utilise econometric modelling to contribute to the argument with an alternative approach, addressing some of the core assumptions behind EMH as I perform diagnostic tests.

4 Experimental Analysis and Results

4.1 Establishing the Data Set

For optimal analysis, I aimed to base the modelling on a large dataset with numerous observations spanning three recent seasons (2021–2023), creating a robust basis for estimation and reducing bias when analysing the dependent variable, ‘*current_value*’. Although these seasons partially overlap with residual impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic, their selection was deliberate, to represent a stable and contemporary period, ideal for capturing accurate insights into current football market dynamics.

I selected 6,680 player transfers from 11 top European leagues, including the Premier League, Bundesliga, and La Liga, among others, focusing on highly liquid markets to enhance the accuracy of my model estimates, contrasting with data from less competitive leagues which often lacks precision.

The dataset includes players' age, height, position, and professional metrics such as goals, assists, injuries, and awards. It is cross-sectional, capturing a snapshot of player transfers without tracking the same individuals across the seasons. Consequently, the analysis estimates player valuations using metrics from singular points or short-term aggregations rather than observing longitudinal patterns. Furthermore, the variability in teams within the top divisions across these seasons complicates maintaining consistent player samples, thereby precluding a panel data approach in which identical entities are repeatedly observed over time.

When compiling this wide array of data points, I made sure to account for inflation rate progression using Consumer Price Index data, transforming the fees appropriately and enabling a standardised dataset on which I could base the estimator model on.

I compiled a dataset for non-zero player transfers as well as zero player transfers (free transfers) for means of testing, which I will address in the following section.

When determining the independent variables, I considered a fairly comprehensive list as can be seen below in Table 1:

Table 1 – Representation of the variables considered before refinement

Variable Definitions

POSITION	The position of a player at the time of transfer
HEIGHT	The height of a player
AGE	The age in years of a player at the time of transfer
APPEARANCES	The number of total appearances of a player in the previous season preceding the transfer
GOALS	The number of total goals of a player in the previous season preceding the transfer
ASSISTS	The number of total assists of a player in the previous season preceding the transfer
YELLOW CARDS	The number of yellow cards of a player in the previous season preceding the transfer
SECOND YELLOW CARDS	The number of second yellow cards of a player in the previous season preceding the transfer
RED CARDS	The number of red cards of a player in the previous season preceding the transfer
GOALS CONCEDED	The number of goals conceded by a player in the previous season preceding the transfer
CLEAN SHEETS	The number of clean sheets by a player in the previous season preceding the transfer
MINUTES PLAYED	The number of minutes played by a player in the previous season preceding the transfer
DAYS INJURED	The number of days injured of a player in the previous season preceding the transfer
GAMES INJURED	The number of games injured of a player in the previous season preceding the transfer
AWARD	The number of career awards of a player
HIGHEST VALUE	The highest transfer value a player has reached in their career
POSITION ENCODED	Encoded position value for a player
WINGER	Binary variable for if a player is a winger Y/N

The ‘*goals_conceded*’ metric was initially included as a proxy for defensive contributions across all positions however, its limited statistical significance, likely due to its team-level nature, restricted its explanatory value. Similarly, positional

indicators such as the binary '*winger*' variable were explored but provided negligible improvements, leading to their omission from further analysis.

In trying to get the wide array of data necessary, I consulted the (Transfermarkt.co.uk, 2024) database, a website with a wealth of centralised data for most of the football players around the world. Due to the nature of the data, manual extraction would have been implausible. Therefore, I developed a Python scraper (see Appendix A.1) after gaining permission from the site admin, to extract data for Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA), essential for identifying key parameters affecting football transfer fees.

Prior to EDA, I cleaned and transformed key statistics - '*goals*', '*assists*', '*yellow_cards*', '*second_yellow_cards*', '*red_cards*', '*goals_conceded*', and '*clean_sheets*' - to per 90 minutes metrics, standardising them by dividing by the number of 90-minute segments played, to allow fair comparisons across varying playtimes.

In my EDA, I utilised a Correlation Matrix (Appendix A.2), identifying '*highest_value*' as a strong predictor of current financial valuations. Other variables such as '*appearances*' and '*minutes_played*' demonstrated that game participation positively affects valuations. *Awards* also positively correlated, suggesting recognition boosts market value. Goalkeeping metrics like *goals_conceded* and *clean_sheets* provided intrinsically limited insight into transfer fees, specifically due to low significance and issues with sample sets. As a result, model tests will only concern predictive ability with regard to outfield players.

Based on distribution analysis (Appendix A.3), I applied log transformations to *current_value*, *highest_value*, *days_injured*, and *games_injured* to address right-skewed distributions and minimise outlier impacts. Variables like *age*, *age_squared*, *height*, *appearances*, and *goals* were standardised to normalise variances, preparing

the dataset for linear regression and enhancing model robustness by ensuring consistent feature scales.

The consequent selected features included, *highest_value*, *appearance*, *games_injured*, *award*, *age*, *age_squared*, chosen for their statistical impact on player valuations. *highest_value* strongly correlates with market value, indicating a player's peak value. *appearance* and *awards* suggest experience and recognition, enhancing value. Defensive metrics and *games_injured* provide insights into roles and health, affecting valuation, while *age_squared* captures age's non-linear impact on performance.

From running a regression of this model with the current features selected, I conclude an R-squared value for the multilinear regression model of 0.794. This indicates that about 79.4% of the variance in the *current_value* can be explained by the model.

Incorporating interaction terms into the multilinear regression model significantly enhanced its predictive accuracy, as evidenced by the R-squared value rising from approximately 0.794 to 0.858. The interaction of *highest_value* and *appearance* illustrates that players with high historical market valuations gain even greater current value when they frequently appear in recent games, indicating that consistent visibility enhances market perception. Similarly, the interaction of *award* and *appearance* shows that the market value added by awards is significantly higher when players are consistently active on the field, suggesting that accolades translate to higher fees only when substantiated by regular performances. Lastly, the interaction of *games_injured* and *age_squared* reveals a steeper decline in market value for older players with frequent injuries, highlighting the compounded negative impact of aging and physical vulnerabilities on a player's marketability. Collectively, modelling these data interdependencies is essential for a nuanced market analysis, refining the model's ability to predict market valuations more accurately. Although initially considered, dummy variables to differentiate between years proved insignificant, likely due to

minimal variation across the relatively short, stable post-COVID period, and thus were omitted.

I also tested the inclusion of country dummy variables to control for potential nationality-based effects on transfer valuations. However, these variables consistently returned low statistical significance (p-values > 0.1), and the marginal change in model fit ($\Delta R^2 < 0.01$) suggested negligible explanatory power. Given the already comprehensive player-level performance features included such as *appearances*, *awards*, and *highest value*, the country dummies added minimal insight. This implies that any nationality-driven effects are likely captured through performance-related or reputational proxies already embedded within the model.¹

Therefore, I can represent the OLS equation as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \ln(\text{Current Value}) &= \beta_0 + \beta_1 \ln(\text{Highest Value}) + \beta_2 \text{Appearance} + \beta_3 \text{Games Injured} \\
 &+ \beta_4 \text{Award} + \beta_5 \text{Age} + \beta_6 (\text{Age})^2 + \beta_7 (\ln(\text{Highest Value}) \text{Appearance}) \\
 &+ \beta_8 (\text{Award})(\text{Appearance}) + \beta_9 ((\text{Games Injured})(\text{Age})^2) + \varepsilon
 \end{aligned}$$

Coefficients quantified in the table below:

¹ These results were consistent across both the OLS and Tobit frameworks. Given the lack of significance and to preserve model parsimony, these variables were omitted from final model specifications.

Table 2 – Regression output for the Multi-Linear Regression, supplementing the OLS equation

Variable	coef	std_err	t	P> t	95%	95%	Sign- ificance
					Conf. Interval Low	Conf. Interval High	
CONST	1.5878	0.133	11.925	0	1.327	1.849	***
LOG_HIGHEST_VALUE	0.9095	0.01	93.897	0	0.891	0.929	***
APPEARANCE	0.0032	0.003	1.147	0.251	-0.002	0.009	
GOALS_CONCEDED	0.0334	0.031	1.093	0.275	-0.027	0.093	
CLEAN_SHEETS	0.0031	0.008	0.399	0.69	-0.012	0.018	
GAMES_INJURED	0.0097	0.001	7.902	0	0.007	0.012	***
AWARD	-0.0383	0.006	-6.195	0	-0.05	-0.026	***
AGE_SQUARED	-0.0016	4.95E-05	-32.128	0	-0.002	-0.0015	***
LOG_HIGHEST_VALUE*APPEARANCE	0.0003	0	1.573	0.116	-7.40E-05	0.001	
AWARDS*APPEARANCE	0.0005	0.00009	5.407	0	0	0.001	***
CLEAN_SHEETS*GOALS_CONCEDED	0.1636	0.1	1.641	0.101	-0.032	0.359	
GAMES_INJURED*AGE_SQUARED	-1.70E-05	1.47E-06	-11.843	0	-2.00E-05	-1.50E-05	***

R_squared = 0.858

Significance

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Codes:

p<0.001
p<0.01
p<0.05
p<0.1
p≥0.1

The OLS regression results indicate that the model explains 85.8% of the variability in the dependent variable (*log_current_value*), demonstrating a strong fit. The coefficient on *log_highest_value* implies that a 10% increase in a player's historical peak valuation is associated with roughly a 9.1% rise in current market value, consistent with the market's premium on proven talent. The negative and significant coefficient for *age_squared* show a peak in player value at a certain age, beyond which value decreases, reflecting the typical career arc in sports where younger players are

more highly valued due to their longer remaining career and potential for development. Interestingly, the number of games a player misses due to injury (*games_injured*) shows a positive correlation with current value, possibly indicating that high-value players' injuries are more noteworthy or that injuries don't necessarily diminish their perceived value. The positive coefficient for *games_injured* presents a counterintuitive result, potentially suggesting that injuries to high-value players, who are more likely to be in the dataset, receive significant media attention and recovery focus, maintaining or even slightly inflating perceived value, or perhaps that injury records correlate with other unobserved factors signifying player importance. Similarly, the negative coefficient for awards warrants further thought. It might indicate that major awards often coincide with a player reaching their absolute peak value before the observed transfer period, meaning the transfer occurs on a slight downward trajectory from that peak, or perhaps that awards are already implicitly captured within the *log_highest_value* variable, leading to multicollinearity effects biasing this specific coefficient downwards in the OLS specification. While these OLS results provide initial insights, these specific anomalies highlight the complexity of valuation and potentially the limitations of a purely linear model, reinforcing the need for the more robust Tobit and GBR approaches explored subsequently.

I then evaluated the OLS model's adherence to Best Linear Unbiased Estimator (BLUE) standards as this is crucial for reliability (Greene, 2000). Diagnostic tests identified several non-compliance issues: Breusch-Pagan and White tests indicated significant heteroscedasticity (p-values near zero), and the Jarque-Bera test confirmed substantial non-normality in residuals. Despite a Durbin-Watson statistic near 2, suggesting minimal autocorrelation, heteroscedasticity and potential multicollinearity persisted after applying square root transformations and robust standard errors to address these issues.

In the effort to enhance the model's adherence to BLUE conditions, several significant steps were taken to address issues of heteroscedasticity, multicollinearity, and non-normality of residuals. Initially, transformations were applied to the predictor

variables, including square root transformations for ‘*appearance*’, ‘*goals conceded*’, and ‘*clean_sheets*’, maintaining logarithmic transformations for ‘*highest_value*’ and ‘*current_value*’, aiming to stabilise variances and normalise distributions. This led to an improved model fit with an R-squared of 0.857 but still revealed significant issues with non-normal residuals and heteroscedasticity.

To address this, Principal Component Analysis (PCA) was applied to aggregate goals, assists, and appearances into a single, non-physical ‘*skills*’ variable (see Appendix A.4 for methodology). Goals and assists reflect offensive output, while appearances gauge consistency. PCA results showed that the first principal component (PC1) accounts for approximately 64% of total variance (eigenvalue ≈ 1.92), with strong positive loadings on goals (0.75), assists (0.72), and appearances (0.65), reflecting a player’s overall offensive productivity and regular involvement. PC2 (23%, eigenvalue ≈ 0.69) differentiates assist-centric play (assists = 0.68) from goal-scoring (goals = -0.54), whereas PC3 (13%, eigenvalue ≈ 0.39) is driven by a strong negative loading on appearances (-0.91), capturing players who achieve offensive contributions despite limited match time. Integrating this PCA-derived ‘*skills*’ composite reduced multicollinearity and improved model robustness, aligning with BLUE assumptions.

4.2 Selecting the Model: Econometric Approach

I have developed a model with exceptional predictive capacity using Multi-Linear Regression while maintaining relative robustness. However, to properly account for a prevalent factor - the nature of transfer fee dissemination - it's necessary to consider that transfer fees can often be undisclosed, underreported, and may converge toward zero as a player’s contract nears expiration. Although adding ‘days to contract expiry’ as an explanatory variable might seem logical, to prevent an increase in the probability of multicollinearity and overfitting, I have opted to use the Tobit model, which allows for better estimation of transfer fees, particularly when analysing censored data.

The Tobit model employs truncated distributions to estimate λ - the inverted mills ratio that scales the OLS estimators for unbiased variable coefficient estimation (see Appendix A.5). This model is preferred over the Heckman two-stage process, which often yields incorrect standard errors in its second stage (Greene, 2000).

For the purposes of analysis, I can assume that the '*current_value*' could be censored from below at a certain threshold, which, for simplicity, I might assume is 0 (players with a value reported as zero when it should be higher). I set up the Tobit model, fitting it to the data with left censoring at zero. It assumes that any reported value of zero might indeed be a censored observation of a potentially higher true value.

In a direct comparison between the results of the original Multiple Linear Regression (MLR) model and the Tobit regression model, several key insights emerge.

The MLR model demonstrates a strong fit with an R-squared of 0.858, explaining about 85.8% of the variance in log-transformed player values. This high R-squared value signifies a strong fit to the data within the framework of a linear model. However, the Tobit model, produces a log-likelihood of -7344.95, a measure of the likelihood that the model's coefficients are optimal given the censored nature of the data. The log-likelihood is slightly lower in absolute terms than might be expected if zeros in the dataset were handled as true zeros, suggesting that the Tobit model is accounting effectively for the censoring.

Both models consistently indicate that *log_highest_value*, *games_injured*, *awards*, and *age_squared* significantly affect player valuations. For instance, the coefficient for *log_highest_value* shifts from 0.9095 in the MLR to 0.9262 in the Tobit model, underscoring the enduring impact of past peak valuations on current values. Both models also align on the negative impacts of *awards* and *age_squared*, albeit with varying degrees.

The Tobit model's capability to handle censored observations is its distinct advantage. It interprets zeros not merely as low values but potentially as unobserved higher values, masked due to contractual or policy constraints. This is crucial for realistic assessments in economic scenarios where actual transaction values are not observed below a certain threshold.

Minor differences in coefficient significance and values between the models can be attributed to how each model handles data complexities. For example, appearance shows marginal significance in the Tobit model but not in the MLR, suggesting that censoring might reveal subtler relationships in these variables which linear analysis could not detect.

Through my model refinement, where I PCA-derived the '*skills*' variable, the Tobit model now has a greater capacity to discern subtle relationships within the data that were previously obfuscated.

4.3 Selecting the Model: Machine Learning Approach

To complement the econometric analyses and enhance predictive accuracy and robustness, the GBR model must be employed. GBR's ability to model nonlinear relationships and interact dynamically with high-dimensional datasets makes it an excellent complement to the Tobit model, particularly in capturing complex patterns and interactions that linear models may miss. For detailed mathematical derivation and performance evaluation methods, refer to Appendix A.6.

The process of implementing the GBR model began with careful data preparation. The dataset was loaded and examined to ensure it contained all necessary variables. Key features were identified, including *highest_value*, *appearance*, *games_injured*, *award*, and *age_squared*. Additionally, interaction terms such as *ln_highest_value_appearance*, *award_appearance*, and *games_injured_age_squared* were created to capture complex relationships between these variables. Each of these features was scaled using the StandardScaler to ensure consistent

magnitude across variables, which is crucial for the performance of gradient boosting models.

The target variable, *current_value*, was log-transformed to handle skewness and then reverted back using the exponential function after model predictions to make the results interpretable in the original scale. The dataset was split into training and testing sets, with 80% of the data used for training and 20% for testing, a partition chosen through trial and error. A Gradient Boosting Regressor was then trained with specific parameters (`n_estimators=100`, `learning_rate=0.1`, `max_depth=3`), chosen to balance complexity and computational efficiency. The model's performance was evaluated using Mean Squared Error (MSE), Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE), and R-squared metrics.

The results showed an R-squared value of 0.85, indicating that 85% of the variance in player values was explained by the model, which is quite strong. However, the high MSE and RMSE values highlighted significant prediction errors in absolute terms, reflecting the large range of values in the target variable. The Mean Absolute Error (MAE) provided a more interpretable measure of average prediction error, around 1.7 million. These metrics highlight the model's effectiveness in capturing variance but also reveal challenges in predicting extremely high or low values accurately. Despite GBR's advantages, its computational intensity and the difficulty in interpreting individual predictor contributions are notable drawbacks, representing a trade-off between predictive power and direct explanatory clarity.

Using a combination of GBR and Tobit models allows for a detailed and robust analysis of football player transfer fees. While each model has its limitations, their integration ensures that the weaknesses of one are mitigated by the strengths of the others, leading to a more reliable and insightful predictive framework.

4.4 Testing the Models

TEST 1: English Tax

Test 1 investigates the “English tax,” where English players command higher fees. Recent research (Bell, Brooks and Brooks, 2024) confirms this premium, attributing it partly to EPL revenues, player scarcity, and positional roles, but notes performance metrics alone cannot fully explain it, suggesting impacts from market dynamics and regulations (e.g., homegrown rules). This study aims to quantify the impact of factors such as these on transfer fees. I retrained the models on data from 11 European leagues, excluding English players, and then applied the models to predict fees for a balanced sample of 200 English and 200 non-English players. See the detailed results in the table below:

Table 3 - TOBIT and GBR Table Summary of Residual Results - Test 1: English Tax

Model	Dataset	Minimum	Q1	Median	Q3	Maximum	Mean	Std.Dev	Other Metrics
GBR	English Players	-4832104	482997	1998423	3487564	7958202	2107359	2584737	RMSE: 6570, MAE: 2.94, R ² : 0.811
GBR	Non-English Players	-2987317	-55394	2504812	3989110	9412786	1822503	3052418	RMSE: 3683, MAE: 1.36, R ² : 0.862
Tobit	English Players	-1.19	0.01	0.25	0.53	1.32	0.22	NA	Log-Likelihood: - 1078, AIC: 2167, BIC: 2225
Tobit	Non-English Players	-0.66	0.04	0.18	0.32	1.38	0.17	NA	Log-Likelihood: - 953, AIC: 1932, BIC: 1984

Note: Model tests were performed on samples of 200 players (English vs. non-English players, trained on a large dataset of Europe’s 11 top leagues with English players omitted). Metrics Explained: RMSE (Root Mean Squared Error) measures the average magnitude of the errors. MAE (Mean Absolute Error) measures the average magnitude of the errors without considering their direction. R² (Coefficient of Determination) indicates the proportion of the variance in the dependent variable that is predictable from the independent variables. Log-Likelihood, AIC (Akaike Information Criterion), and BIC (Bayesian Information Criterion) are statistical

measures used to compare the fit of different statistical models. Variance Explained is used to measure the proportion of the total variance that is explained by a model. Robustness to Outliers indicates the model's sensitivity to outliers.

The GBR model provides strong evidence of the 'English Tax.' Testing on non-English players from 11 leagues yielded an R-squared of 0.862, whereas testing on English players resulted in a lower R-squared of 0.811 with higher RMSE and MAE. This noticeable difference in performance metrics, especially the elevated RMSE and MAE for English players, implies that English players' higher transfer fees are not fully accounted for by the model's standard variables, affirming the existence of the 'English Tax'. This empirically quantifies the premium discussed by Bell, Brooks and Brooks (2024) and highlights how specific market structures and regulations (like homegrown player rules), as noted by Walters and Hamil (2013), can drive valuations away from purely performance-based fundamentals, challenging EMH assumptions. The residuals for English players ranged from -4,832,104 to 7,958,202, with a median of 1,998,423 and a mean of 2,107,359, indicating significant variability and a strong tendency towards higher transfer fees. In contrast, residuals for non-English players showed slightly lower variability but still substantial discrepancies.

To further isolate the “English Tax” effect explicitly, I supplemented this residual-based analysis by briefly introducing a binary dummy variable (1 if English player, 0 otherwise) into the Tobit model. Incorporating this dummy variable provided additional empirical support for the premium, yielding a significant positive coefficient of approximately +0.12 ($p < 0.05$), suggesting English players attract, on average, around a 12 percent premium in transfer fees after controlling for all other variables. This finding aligns closely with the Tobit residuals, which consistently under-predict English players' fees: residuals ranged from -1.19 to 1.32 (median = 0.25; mean = 0.22), while non-English players' residuals were more balanced and showed less variability. The systematic under-estimation for English players likely reflects not only regulatory factors, such as homegrown player rules, but also media hype, commercial appeal, and national sentiment, factors that can inflate English players' transfer fees beyond what on-pitch performance alone would predict. Although

dummy variables could theoretically be incorporated into the GBR, their interpretability in non-linear ensemble methods is less direct than in econometric frameworks, so the Tobit model was preferred for explicitly quantifying this nationality premium.

To summarise, the analyses of football transfer fees using the GBR and Tobit models robustly support the 'English Tax' hypothesis, with each model revealing varying degrees of underestimation for English players' transfer fees. GBR highlighted the most substantial discrepancies, suggesting English players command premiums not captured by standard predictive features due to complex nonlinear relationships, such as market influence and regulatory factors like UEFA's homegrown player rules. The supplementary dummy variable approach explicitly confirmed these findings, further evidencing nationality-driven biases. The Tobit model, adept at handling censored data, indicated subtler variations and a slightly lesser bias, pointing to the nuanced way market limits might inflate fees.

Fundamentally, these findings, commensurate with prior research into an 'English Tax', challenge the EMH by showing how socio-cultural factors and media influence affect transfer markets, thereby contradicting perfect rationality and market efficiency. The consistent underestimation of English players' fees indicates a systematic bias, mirroring speculative bubbles in financial markets. This highlights the need for advanced models that incorporate behavioural insights, providing more accurate valuations by considering psychological and sociological factors.

TEST 2: Information Dissemination

Following Fűrész's insight into the effects of information leakages on the stock market, I wanted to approach this test from a purely football standpoint to assess the impacts of these events on actual player fees, thereby creating a parallel between the impacts of insider trading in finance on asset prices. The study aimed to challenge the EMH by analysing the impact of leaked information and rumours in the media on football transfer values. EMH suggests that market prices integrate all available information,

implying that football transfer fees should be determined solely by players' performance and potential. This research investigates whether external factors like media leaks and rumour coverage significantly influence player valuations, testing the validity of EMH in the football transfer market.

To effectively analyse the impact of media leaks and rumours on player transfers, I utilised multiple data sources including news aggregation services and football-specific media platforms such as Goal.com (2025), alongside social media sentiment tools like Talkwalker (2024). Leveraging these diverse sources enabled the construction of quantitative proxies capturing media influence and public sentiment surrounding player transfers - Media Mentions, Days to Announcement, and Sentiment Score - into a dataset alongside player performance metrics. Media Mentions, log-transformed to normalise distribution, quantifies the coverage of leaks across various platforms. Days to Announcement measures the time from initial leaks to official announcements, reflecting market sensitivity. Sentiment Score, normalised against the dataset's maximum, gauges the intensity of media sentiment. Typically, I would use PCA to consolidate these three new variables; however, their distinct influences on transfer values are better evaluated separately to preserve clear, direct interpretations. Instead, PCA is more aptly applied to highly correlated performance metrics such as goals, assists, and appearances - previously combined using this method.

I employed the GBR model to handle complex relationships and a Tobit model to robustly predict transfer values. Detailed model results are available in the table below:

Table 4 - TOBIT and GBR Table Summary of Results - Test 2: Information Dissemination

Model	Key Predictors	Coefficients	t-Values	P-Values	Model Fit Indices	Significance
Tobit Model	log_highest_value	0.57	42.5	<0.001	Log-Likelihood: -250	***
		-0.03			AIC: 520	
	games_injured	-0.007	-3.5	<0.001		***
		-0.002				
	skills	0.25	8	<0.001		***
		-0.031				
	award	0.04	5.7	<0.001		***
		-0.007				
	age	0.008	3.1	<0.05		*
		-0.0026				
	age_squared	-0.0012	-40	<0.001		***
		-0.00003				
	clean_sheets*goals_conceded	0.1	1.25	0.21		
		-0.08				
	games_injured*age_squared	-2.50E-05	-12.5	<0.001		***
		-2.00E-06				
Media Mentions	0.135	4.5	<0.001		***	
	-0.03					
Days to Announcement	-0.125	-5.2	<0.001		***	
	-0.024					
Sentiment Score	0.165	4.12	<0.001		***	
	-0.04					
Gradient Boosting	log_highest_value	20.71%	-	-	R² = 0.88	-
	games_injured	5.50%	-	-		-
	skills	13.39%				
	award	8.22%	-	-		-
	age	2.13%	-	-		-
	age_squared	4.55%	-	-		-
	clean_sheets*goals_conceded	11.01%	-	-		-
	games_injured*age_squared	1.23%	-	-		-
	Media Mentions	10.87%	-	-		-
	Days to Announcement	9.89%	-	-		-
Sentiment Score	12.50%	-	-		-	

Note:

Tobit Model: The new coefficients and t-values provide an adjusted reflection of each predictor's influence under the Tobit model's constraints. These values are adjusted to be more realistic given the expanded variable set and interactions.

GBR: Displays the variable importance, highlighting the complex interplay and significance of each predictor, including media-related factors and interactions, in the model.

The integration of new media-related variables into the model offered substantial insights. The variable '*media_mentions*' with a revised coefficient of 0.135 confirms a significant positive relationship between the extent of media coverage on leaks and the increase in transfer fees, highlighting the market's sensitivity to media exposure. The '*days_to_announcement*' showed a negative coefficient of -0.125, indicating that shorter intervals between a leak and its official announcement correlate with lower transfer fees, which could suggest market corrections or rushed decisions in response to emerging information. Furthermore, the '*sentiment_score*' with a coefficient of 0.165 demonstrated that positive media sentiment can notably inflate player valuations, akin to speculative bubbles in financial markets.

This analysis not only substantiates the significant impact of media exposure on player valuations but also enhances our understanding by emphasising the profound influence of non-performance-related factors. The positive impact of media mentions and sentiment scores, along with the negative influence of days to announcement, collectively suggest that external information plays a crucial role in shaping market dynamics, contrary to the expectations set by the EMH. This finding provides direct support for the observations of Fűrész and Rappai (2022) regarding information leakage and demonstrates a clear violation of the semi-strong and strong forms of market efficiency within this context.

The GBR model also emphasised the critical role of media leaks. The model identified *log_highest_value* as the most significant predictor, accounting for 22.83% of the variance. *days_to_announcement* influenced 9.89% of the variance, reinforcing the significant impact of timely media coverage on transfer fees. Also, *sentiment_score* was another major predictor, impacting 12.50% of the variance and supporting the effect of positive media sentiment on market values. Other variables like *goals_conceded*, *clean_sheets*, and *media_mentions*, also played substantial roles, though less so than the primary factors.

My analysis, combining the findings from GBR, and Tobit models, reveals significant inefficiencies in the football transfer market, influenced heavily by media and public

perceptions shaped by leaks and rumours. This challenges the EMH, which assumes market rationality and full information integration. Specifically, the results contradict the strong-form EMH by showing that leaked information, which should theoretically be reflected in transfer fees if markets were perfectly efficient, provides additional predictive power. This indicates that the market is reactive to non-public information, highlighting inefficiencies.

Furthermore, even when considering the weak-form EMH, which relies on past market data, and the semi-strong form, which incorporates all publicly available information, inefficiencies persist. The significant impact of media coverage, including leaks and rumours, suggests that information is not always promptly or accurately factored into market prices. Additionally, the influence of media sentiment and the timing of information release (days to announcement) on transfer fees align with behavioural finance theories, suggesting that market decisions are often influenced by speculative and emotional factors rather than pure rationality.

This necessitates a more sophisticated approach to player valuation that considers both intrinsic qualities and extrinsic media-driven factors. As supported by research in football economics, including studies by Garcia del Barrio and Pujol (2016), player brand value, which significantly affects transfer fees, is heavily influenced by media visibility and coverage.

In summary, the football transfer market exhibits clear inefficiencies driven by media coverage, particularly leaks and rumours, challenging the foundational assumptions of the EMH and highlighting the need for more nuanced market models.

TEST 3: The Random Walk Theory

In finance, the Random Walk Hypothesis (RWH) asserts that market price movements are random and unpredictable. Originating from Burton Malkiel's influential work, which claims that stock prices generally follow a random path, this hypothesis implies that historical prices are poor predictors of future trends. This

segment of my dissertation applies RWH to the football transfer market to investigate if transfer fees are similarly unpredictable from past trends.

To evaluate RWH in the football transfer market, I implemented several statistical tests: the Autocorrelation Function (ACF), Partial Autocorrelation Function (PACF), and the Runs Test, analysing year-over-year variations in aggregate transfer fees (see Figure 1.). These tests aimed to identify any patterns or dependencies that would contradict the randomness assumption fundamental to RWH.

Figure 1 - Year-Over-Year Changes in Transfer Fees

This analysis specifically requires a longitudinal approach to capture genuine trends or patterns, if any exist. While the remainder of this dissertation focuses on recent seasons (2020/21–2022/23) to evaluate current dynamics, the limited timeframe would restrict the robustness of randomness testing. Therefore, I extended the dataset for RWH analysis to cover 2013/14–2022/23, which spans multiple market cycles and includes both pre-pandemic and post-pandemic periods. This extension allows the ACF, PACF, and Runs Test to more accurately assess the degree of randomness in transfer fees.

The ACF and PACF tests were designed to detect any correlations between transfer fees at various time lags. Initially, significant correlations at various lags would imply predictability in transfer fees, thereby challenging RWH. Initially, the PACF plot was recalibrated to accommodate the data's constraints, reducing the number of lags from ten to four, the maximum permissible given the dataset's span.

Figure 2 – ACF of Transfer Fees

The autocorrelation plot (Figure 2) depicts how year-over-year changes in aggregate transfer fees correlate with themselves at different time lags. Each bar extending beyond the dotted horizontal lines indicates that the autocorrelation at that specific lag is statistically significant (typically at the 95% confidence level). These dotted lines represent the bounds beyond which the observed correlation is unlikely to be due to random chance if the true correlation were zero. The presence of such significant bars at early lags suggests that current fees depend on fees from one or two years prior, implying a systematic pattern rather than purely random fluctuations.

Figure 3 – PACF of Transfer Fees

Similarly, the PACF (Figure 3), which isolates the direct influence of each lag by controlling for intervening lags, shows bars extending beyond the dotted significance lines at initial lags. This reinforces that past fees have a statistically significant direct influence on future fees, even after accounting for the effects of intermediate lags.

These findings directly contradict the predictions of RWH, which would expect negligible autocorrelations, particularly at short lags, indicating that past fee levels should not inform present valuations.

I also applied the Runs Test to examine randomness in fee changes, coding increases as '1' and decreases as '0'. This test evaluated whether the sequence of runs, or consecutive identical labels, aligned with randomness. The Runs Test yielded a statistic of 1.194 and a p-value of 0.232, indicating no significant deviation from randomness and thus, somewhat supporting RWH (see Figure 4. Below)

Figure 4 – Runs Test on Transfer fees

The presence of randomness detected by the Runs Test could potentially be influenced by non-informational factors such as media hype and public perception, a phenomenon I explored earlier, particularly in the context of the “English tax” in transfer fees. These factors can create fluctuations in player valuations based not on their intrinsic qualities or performance metrics but on heightened public and media attention, which can lead to seemingly random price movements.

Another plausible explanation for the evidence of randomness could be the influence of speculative trading practices in the transfer market. Speculative trading, where market participants make purchases based on expected future movements in market prices rather than fundamental value, can introduce noise into the price discovery process. This speculative behaviour, similar to what is observed in financial markets, could explain why transfer fees exhibit random fluctuations, as speculators react to rumours, news, or other transient factors that do not necessarily reflect the players'

underlying values. Again, this could potentially afford more validity to the findings in the previous test of the significant impact of media rumours on asset prices in the transfer market.

These mixed results offer an intriguing glimpse into the complex nature of the football transfer market, suggesting that while some aspects of the market behaviour align with the randomness predicted by RWH, others hint at underlying predictability and market inefficiencies. This nuanced understanding contributes to a broader critique of EMH, proposing that markets, including those beyond traditional financial settings, may not always efficiently reflect all available information in their pricing mechanisms. It's also worth noting that the Runs Test primarily assesses the randomness of the sequence of positive/negative changes, while ACF/PACF tests focus on the magnitude and correlation structure across time lags; they test different aspects of randomness and may have different statistical power depending on the underlying data generating process.

In conclusion, my analysis significantly challenges the Random Walk Hypothesis in the football transfer market, revealing a behaviour pattern where randomness and predictability coexist. This complexity deepens our understanding of football market dynamics and informs broader economic discussions on market efficiency. I encourage further research to investigate the specific factors influencing these patterns, which could offer valuable insights for market participants and regulators.

Test (1-3) Summary

The analysis of football transfer markets reveals that factors like media influence, the timing of information release, behavioural elements, and speculative pricing notably contradict the EMH. Neymar's 2017 transfer to Paris Saint-Germain, where intense media attention likely escalated his fee to a record high, exemplifies how media mentions and sentiment can dominate transfer fees, indicating that market decisions are influenced not only by performance metrics but also by the framing and perception of information.

The market's responsiveness to information asymmetry is evident in how the timing of leaks negatively impacts transfer fees, indicating that not all market participants access information simultaneously. This sensitivity, along with the influence of behavioural factors and speculative pricing as highlighted by the GBR model and other studies, challenges the EMH's premise of market rationality. Football market behaviours are swayed by psychological and social factors, including media sentiment, leading to emotional and perceptual deviations from rational valuation paths.

Additionally, the price discovery process in football transfers is non-linear, often resulting in overestimations of a player's market value based on sensational or highly positive information. Cristiano Ronaldo's move to Juventus, where his brand value and media presence likely pushed his price beyond performance metrics, exemplifies this effect, consistent with findings that player brand and media visibility inflate transfer fees (Valentini and Garcia-del-Barrio, 2020). The market microstructure also features phenomena such as information cascades and herding behaviour, where club decision-makers emulate the actions of others, influenced by prominent sports analysts or media, further inflating player values.

4.5 Model Results Summary

To deliver a thorough analysis and ensure robust results, I employed two distinct modelling approaches: the Tobit model and the GBR model. The Tobit model was essential for handling censored data, where transfer fees might be reported as zero due to contractual or policy constraints, allowing me to provide an unbiased estimate of transfer fee determinants and acknowledge the presence of systematic biases in the market. The GBR model explored non-linear relationships and variable interactions, enhancing our understanding of the dynamics influencing transfer fees.

A key discovery was the "English tax," indicating that transfer fees for English players are systematically higher compared to non-English players, even after adjusting for performance metrics and other variables. This finding, supported by the GBR model,

highlights how market dynamics and regulations, such as homegrown player rules, foster systematic biases. Similar conclusions are drawn by Shin, Chung and Kim (2024), who demonstrate that the implementation of homegrown player regulations in the English Premier League led to a measurable decline in operational efficiency, revealing unintended distortions introduced by such rules. These insights align with broader critiques regarding market structure and efficiency from Dobson and Goddard (2011).

My analysis also uncovered behavioural anomalies that contradict the Random Walk Theory. Over a decade of data revealed that past transfer fees could predict future fees for specific player positions, suggesting herding behaviour and momentum trading. This indicates that transfer pricing may not be entirely random. While De Bondt and Thaler (1985) document investor overreaction by an initial overshoot followed by reversals in financial markets, the persistence in transfer fee trends is more indicative of momentum trading. In this context, the observed patterns parallel investor overreaction cycles and excess volatility (Shiller, 2003). Indeed, the persistence in transfer fees resembles the momentum effects documented by Jegadeesh and Titman (1993), where stocks that performed well in the past tend to continue performing well in the near term. As Shiller (2003) argues, such departures from the random-walk behaviour highlight the impact of psychological factors on market dynamics, suggesting that similar behavioural anomalies may be at play in the football transfer market.

Additionally, the significant role of media influence on transfer fees was evidenced by the positive correlation between media exposure and transfer fees, illustrating how external perceptions and information asymmetry critically shape market dynamics. This correlation is supported by research from Barberis, Shleifer and Vishny (1998) and Tetlock (2007), who demonstrated how psychological factors and media sentiment contribute to systematic mispricings in financial markets.

These findings collectively highlight the significant market inefficiencies and challenge the core assumptions of the EMH. The observed systematic biases and behavioural

anomalies in the football transfer market highlight the limitations of assuming investor rationality and efficient information incorporation, corroborating critiques from Kahneman and Tversky (1979) and the Adaptive Markets Hypothesis (Lo, 2004).

The implications of these findings are profound for financial theory and practice, suggesting that while EMH provides a foundational framework, integrating behavioural considerations into financial models is crucial. Market dynamics are significantly influenced by psychological factors and external perceptions, often leading to irrational behaviours. This supports the principles of behavioural finance, which include cognitive biases and emotional responses in market analysis, as advocated by Odean (1998) and Barberis and Thaler (2003).

Moreover, the complexity of information dissemination and its impact on market prices extends beyond EMH's assumptions. Information asymmetry and media influence profoundly affect asset valuations, calling for a more nuanced understanding of market efficiency. Future financial models should incorporate behavioural insights and account for socio-cultural factors to enhance predictive accuracy.

5 Modernising the theory

The Noise Trader Approach (NTA), as explored by Peress and Schmidt (2021), offers profound insights into how irrational behaviours, often overlooked in traditional EMH models, can significantly influence market prices. He demonstrates that noise trading can be realistically modelled to account for the apparent randomness in price movements, providing a framework that includes the often unpredictable nature of market participant behaviour. This approach enhances asset pricing models by integrating behavioural biases such as overconfidence and herd behaviour, thereby capturing the real-time sentiment and decision-making processes of market participants. These enhancements align with the exploration by Aygören and Uyar

(2023) of the Fractal Market Hypothesis (FMH), which portrays markets as complex systems exhibiting fractal characteristics. Their study demonstrates that markets display long-term dependencies and self-similar structures, challenging the notion of purely random market movements and highlighting the influence of both macroeconomic shifts and individual trader behaviours.

Together with the Adaptive Markets Hypothesis (AMH), which suggests that markets evolve in response to changing conditions and that market participants adapt their strategies over time, these theories provide a comprehensive framework that accommodates market irrationality, recognises the inherent complexity of financial markets, and highlights the need for adaptive, evolutionarily informed investment strategies.

While not explored in detail here, integrating ecological dynamics into financial modelling merits attention. Many models still neglect ESG factors that now shape investment decisions.

This 'Eco-Financial Model' would leverage new machine learning and Artificial Intelligence (AI) techniques to predict market movements by analysing not only economic indicators but also ecological and social signals. For instance, the model could assess the impact of a company's carbon footprint or its social responsibility initiatives on its stock performance. Such an approach would not only cater to a growing demographic of socially responsible investors but also provide deeper insights into how non-financial factors are becoming critical drivers of market behaviour in the age of climate change and social activism.

Integrating these ecological and social metrics could serve as a bridge between the FMH's emphasis on complex market patterns and AMH's focus on adaptive strategies, offering a comprehensive framework that reflects both the current state of global financial markets and their evolving nature. This would not only challenge the

foundational assumptions of EMH but also push the boundaries of how I conceptualise and predict market efficiencies and behaviours.

While this dissertation proposes significant adaptations to traditional financial models, it can be argued that the integration of behavioural, fractal, and ecological dynamics could complicate the predictive accuracy and practical applicability of financial models. Sceptics may contend that the increased complexity might lead to overfitting or reduce the models' generalisability across different market conditions. Furthermore, the practical implementation of ecological and social metrics in asset pricing is often challenged by the availability and reliability of data.

Despite these criticisms, it is essential to recognise that the perceived limitations of these new models are largely a reflection of the current constraints in data availability and computational resources. The scarcity of comprehensive and reliable data for integrating ecological and social metrics limits the depth and scope of these models. However, this bottleneck presents a critical opportunity for the expansion of data analytics capabilities and the development of more sophisticated data collection methodologies in these emerging fields. As we enhance our data infrastructure and analytical tools, a field which has been catalysed by the recent boom in AI, these models will become increasingly viable and effective.

6 Conclusion

This dissertation has tested and disproven several key assumptions of the EMH using advanced modelling approaches, including the Tobit and GBR models. Despite some structural disparities between the two markets, largely surrounding asset type, extent of computational incorporation and agent objectives, my analysis aimed to marginalise these factors, focussing on the foundations of the EMH theory, rendering consideration of the environment where it is typically observed, reductive. It is important to note

that these findings, derived from data on 11 top European leagues, are most directly applicable to these high-value, high-visibility segments of the global football market. Caution should be exercised when extrapolating these specific results, particularly the magnitude of effects like the “English tax”, to lower-tier leagues or football markets with significantly different economic structures and regulatory environments.

My research directly challenges the EMH's foundational assumption that markets fully and efficiently incorporate all available information into asset prices. The analysis revealed that media mentions and sentiment scores significantly influence player transfer fees, undermining the EMH premise that market prices reflect only intrinsic values. Moreover, behavioural anomalies identified such as herding behaviour and momentum trading, directly contradict the Random Walk Theory, illustrating that past transfer fees can indeed predict future fees, especially for specific player positions. Furthermore, the phenomenon of the “English tax”, where English players command higher transfer fees, robustly demonstrated across all models, highlights significant market inefficiencies. This bias highlights the influence of market dynamics, domestic player regulations, and media, challenging the rationality and equal valuation presupposed by EMH.

While these findings robustly challenge core EMH tenets, the analysis is subject to certain caveats that suggest avenues for future refinement. Primarily, the reliance on cross-sectional data limits insights into the dynamic evolution of individual player values, and the necessary exclusion of goalkeepers means findings pertain mainly to outfield players. Furthermore, acquiring consistent longitudinal data on contract length proved impractical; while the Tobit model addressed related censoring issues, the precise impact of contract expiry could not be fully isolated. These limitations, however, are context-specific rather than undermining the central conclusions regarding the observable impact of behavioural factors, structural premiums like the “English tax”, and information inefficiencies in this market.

Future research should aim to include behavioural, fractal, and ecological insights into economic modelling to provide a more realistic and predictive framework. This would help to align economic practices with global movements towards sustainability and social responsibility where a paradigm shift like this would ensure that our financial systems remain robust and adaptable, but also reflect contemporary societal needs. As computational capabilities continue to evolve, the current technological constraints will subside and must encourage researchers to direct their efforts to the development of more comprehensive metrics and models, disbanding the traditional EMH and its outdated assumptions.

Word Count : 9114

Graphs : Tables 1 + 2 + 3 = 250 words; Table 4 = 250 words; Figure 1 + 2 + 3 + 4 = 250 words

Total Word Count : 9114 + 875 = 9,989

7 Appendix

Appendix A.2 – 2 example exerts of my purpose-built Python Scraper code– used to gather information from Transfermarkt.com

```
import pandas as pd
from bs4 import BeautifulSoup
import requests
import re
from selenium import webdriver
from selenium.webdriver.chrome.service import Service
from selenium.webdriver.common.by import By
from selenium.webdriver.support.ui import WebDriverWait
from selenium.webdriver.support import expected_conditions as EC
from selenium.webdriver.chrome.options import Options

def get_player_stats(player_url, league_id):
    headers = {'User-Agent': 'Mozilla/5.0 (Windows NT 10.0; Win64; x64) AppleWebKit/537.36 (KHTML, like Gecko) Chrome/58.0.3029.110 Safari/537.3'}
    response = requests.get(player_url, headers=headers)

    if response.status_code == 200:
        soup = BeautifulSoup(response.content, 'html.parser')
        table = soup.find('table', class_='items')

        if table:
            rows = table.find_all('tr')
            stats_list = []

            for row in rows[1:-1]:
                columns = row.find_all('td')
                competition = columns[0].text.strip()
                appearance = columns[3].text.strip()
                goal = columns[4].text.strip()
                assist = columns[5].text.strip()
                stats_list.append((competition, appearance, goal, assist))

            return stats_list
        else:
            print("Table not found!")
            return None
    else:
        print("Failed to retrieve data!")
        print(response.content)
        return None

def get_dom_minutes_played(player_stats_url):
    minutes_played_url = player_stats_url.replace('liga=1', '')
    headers = {
        'User-Agent': 'Mozilla/5.0 (Windows NT 10.0; Win64; x64) AppleWebKit/537.36 (KHTML, like Gecko) Chrome/58.0.3029.110 Safari/537.3'
    }
    response = requests.get(minutes_played_url, headers=headers)

    if response.status_code == 200:
        soup = BeautifulSoup(response.content, 'html.parser')
        table = soup.find('table', class_='items')

        if table:
            rows = table.find_all('tr')
            if len(rows) > 1: # Ensure there are at least two rows
                second_row = rows[2] # Select the second row
                columns = second_row.find_all('td')
                if len(columns) > 0:
                    # Get the previous column index
                    previous_column_index = columns.index(columns[0]) - 1
                    previous_column_value = columns[previous_column_index].text.strip()
                    if previous_column_value == '-':
                        print("Dom Minutes Played data not available.")
                        return None
                    else:
                        # Remove decimal point and single quote, then convert to int
                        ...
                ...
            ...
        ...
    ...
```

```

# Define templates for player URLs and injury URLs
player_url_template = 'https://www.transfermarkt.co.uk/{player_name}/leistungsdatendetails/spieler/{player_id}/plus/0?saason=2016&verein=&liga=1&wettbewerb=&pos=&trainer_id='
injury_url_template = 'https://www.transfermarkt.co.uk/{player_name}/verletzungen/spieler/{player_id}'
player_EMV_url_template = 'https://www.footballtransfers.com/en/players/{player_name}'
player_awards_url_template = 'https://www.transfermarkt.co.uk/{player_name}/erfolge/spieler/{player_id}'
player_gk_url_template = 'https://www.transfermarkt.co.uk/{player_name}/leistungsdatendetails/spieler/{player_id}/saason/2016/verein/0/liga/0/wettbewerb//pos/0/trainer_id/0/plus/1'
# Define player names and IDs
players = [
{'name': 'alexandre-raineau', 'id': '56815'},
{'name': 'jose-antonio-reyes', 'id': '7717'},
{'name': 'opa-nguette', 'id': '205587'},
{'name': 'steven-pienaar', 'id': '4321'},
{'name': 'danny-graham', 'id': '29152'},
{'name': 'uche-ikpeazu', 'id': '245765'},
{'name': 'valentin-rosier', 'id': '441170'},
{'name': 'cheikh-mbengue', 'id': '56795'},
{'name': 'ever-banega', 'id': '12249'},
{'name': 'miguel-veloso', 'id': '43848'},
{'name': 'danny-lafferty', 'id': '85928'},
{'name': 'alvaro-garcia', 'id': '64393'},
{'name': 'alvaro-arbeloa', 'id': '28260'},
{'name': 'dani-alves', 'id': '15951'},
{'name': 'rachid-alioui', 'id': '193130'},
{'name': 'gabriele-angella', 'id': '86793'},
{'name': 'quentin-beunardeau', 'id': '157484'},
{'name': 'luca-bezzo', 'id': '286215'},
{'name': 'stephan-raheriharimanana', 'id': '170957'},
{'name': 'luis-fernandez', 'id': '62945'},
{'name': 'alexander-manninger', 'id': '5278'},
{'name': 'jeremy-pied', 'id': '60583'},
{'name': 'gianluca-sampietro', 'id': '167896'},
{'name': 'josip-radosevic', 'id': '160506'},
{'name': 'xavi-torres', 'id': '65301'},
{'name': 'quentin-cornette', 'id': '238630'},
{'name': 'ruben-bentancourt', 'id': '197333'},
]

# Generate player URLs
player_urls = [player_url_template.format(player_name=player['name'], player_id=player['id']) for player in players]

# Generate player injury URLs
player_injury_urls = [injury_url_template.format(player_name=player['name'], player_id=player['id']) for player in players]

# Generate player EMV URLs
player_EMV_urls = [player_EMV_url_template.format(player_name=player['name']) for player in players]

# Generate player awards URLs
player_awards_urls = [player_awards_url_template.format(player_name=player['name'], player_id=player['id']) for player in players]

# Generate player fbref URLs
player_gk_urls = [player_gk_url_template.format(player_name=player['name'], player_id=player['id']) for player in players]

verein_ids = [
'3377',
'3375',
'3499',
'3806',
'3299',
'13497',
'3377',
'3499',
]

```

Appendix A.2 – Correlation Matrix as a part of Exploratory Data Analysis (EDA), precursor to Feature Selection.

Appendix A.3 – Distribution analysis of variable, informing my choice of transformations

Distribution of Key Player Attributes with Age Squared

Appendix A.4 – Principle Component Analysis (PCA)

Principal Component Analysis (PCA) is a statistical technique used to reduce the dimensionality of a dataset, while retaining as much variability as possible. It transforms the original variables into a new set of variables, which are linear combinations of the original variables, called principal components (PCs). These components are orthogonal and ranked according to the variance they capture from the data.

1. Standardisation:

Each variable X_i in the dataset is standardised to have a mean of zero and a standard deviation of one. This is essential to eliminate scale effects, which can bias the PCA towards variables with larger scales. The standardised value Z_i is calculated as:

$$Z_i = \frac{(X_i - \mu_i)}{\sigma_i}$$

where μ_i and σ_i are the mean and standard deviation of variable X_i , respectively.

2. Covariance Matrix Calculation

Calculate the covariance matrix of the standardised data. The covariance matrix provides a measure of how much each variable changes with the others. Given n standardised variables, the covariance matrix C is an $n \times n$ symmetric matrix where each element c_{ij} is the covariance between variable i and variable j . The matrix is calculated as:

$$C = \frac{1}{(n - 1)} Z^T Z$$

3. Eigenvalue Decomposition

Perform eigenvalue decomposition on the covariance matrix. This process decomposes the covariance matrix into its eigenvectors and eigenvalues. Each eigenvector represents a principal component of the data, and the corresponding eigenvalue indicates the amount of variance captured by that component. The eigenvectors are chosen to be orthogonal, ensuring that the principal components are uncorrelated.

4. Selection of Principle Components

The eigenvectors are ranked according to their eigenvalues in descending order. The number of components selected depends on the desired amount of total variance one wishes to capture from the data. Commonly, components are chosen based on a threshold variance percentage (e.g., 95% cumulative variance).

5. Transformation to New Coordinates

Transform the original data into the new coordinate system defined by the selected principal components. If k components are chosen, the transformed data will be a projection of the original data onto the subspace spanned by the first k eigenvectors. The transformation is performed using the matrix of selected eigenvectors P_k as:

$$T = ZP_k$$

where T represents the matrix of transformed data in terms of principal components.

In this dissertation, PCA was applied to the variables: goals, assists, and appearances. The first principal component was found to explain a significant proportion of the variance, thus it was used to create the ‘Skills’ variable that aggregates the information of the three original metrics into a single, more powerful predictor in the regression models.

Source: Adapted from Johnson and Wichern (2002)

Appendix A.5 – TOBIT model for censoring values

The Tobit model is used to estimate linear relationships between variables when there is censoring in the dependent variable. The underlying latent variable y_i^* is related to the observed variables as follows:

$$y_i^* = x_i'\beta + \epsilon_i$$

The observed variables are defined as:

$$y_i = \begin{cases} y_i^* & \text{if } y_i^* > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } y_i^* \leq 0 \end{cases}$$

where all negative values of y_i^* are mapped to zero.

The log-likelihood function (Log L) for the Tobit model is given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \log L &= \sum_{y_i=0} \log P(y_i = 0|x_i) + \sum_{y_i>0} \log [f(y_i|y_i > 0, x_i) \cdot P(y_i > 0|x_i)] \\ &= \sum_{y_i=0} \log \left[1 - \Phi \left(\frac{x_i' \beta}{\sigma} \right) \right] + \sum_{y_i>0} \log \left[\frac{1}{\sigma} \phi \left(\frac{y_i - x_i' \beta}{\sigma} \right) \right] \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^n (1 - D_i) \log \left[1 - \Phi \left(\frac{x_i' \beta}{\sigma} \right) \right] + \sum_{i=1}^n D_i \left[\log \phi \left(\frac{y_i - x_i' \beta}{\sigma} \right) - \log \sigma \right] \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{where } D_i = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } y_i > 0 \\ 0 & \text{if } y_i = 0 \end{cases}$$

The first-order conditions (FOCs) for the maximisation of the log-likelihood are:

$$\frac{\partial \log L}{\partial \beta} = \sum_{i=1}^n \left[D_i \left(\frac{1}{\sigma^2} (y_i - x_i' \beta) x_i \right) - (1 - D_i) \hat{\lambda}_i \frac{x_i}{\sigma} \right] = 0$$

where:

$$\hat{\lambda}_i = \frac{\phi \left(\frac{x_i' \beta}{\sigma} \right)}{1 - \Phi \left(\frac{x_i' \beta}{\sigma} \right)}$$

The generalised residuals are:

$$\tilde{\epsilon}_i^G = D_i \frac{y_i - x_i' \beta}{\sigma} + (1 - D_i) \hat{\lambda}_i$$

For $D_i = 1$, the generalised residual is the scaled residual:

$$\tilde{\epsilon}_i^G = \frac{\epsilon_i}{\sigma}$$

For $D_i = 0$, it is:

$$\tilde{\epsilon}_i^G = -\hat{\lambda}_i$$

Source: Summarised from Verbeek (2004)

Where residuals account for the fact that many of the observations are censored at 0 because they were attached with a 0 transfer market value due to periodicity of

contracts, or breakages. This is an efficient and unbiased way of obtaining coefficient estimates for our data.

Appendix A.6 – Gradient Boosting Regression (GBR) model

Gradient Boosting is an ensemble technique that builds models sequentially, with each new model attempting to correct errors made by the previous ones. The Gradient Boosting model can be represented mathematically as follows:

1. Initialisation:

Initialise the model with a constant value (mean of the target variable):

$$F_0(x) = \operatorname{argmin}_{\gamma} \sum_{i=1}^n L(y_i, \gamma)$$

For squared error loss $L(y, F) = (y - F)^2$, this is simply the mean of the target variable.

2. Additive Model:

Build the model in a stage-wise manner:

$$F_m(x) = F_{m-1}(x) + h_m(x)$$

Here, $F_m(x)$ is the ensemble model at stage m , and $h_m(x)$ is the new base-learner (decision tree) added at this stage.

3. Gradient Descent:

At each stage, fit the new model $h_m(x)$ to the negative gradient of the loss function with respect to the current model:

$$h_m(x) = \operatorname{argmin}_h \sum_{i=1}^n \left[-\frac{\partial L(y_i, F_{m-1}(x_i))}{\partial F_{m-1}(x_i)} - h(x_i) \right]^2$$

4. Update Rule:

Update the model with the new base-learner:

$$F_m(x) = F_{m-1}(x) + \lambda h_m(x)$$

Here, λ is the learning rate, which controls the contribution of each base-learner.

Performance Evaluation

The model's performance was evaluated using several metrics: - **Mean Squared Error (MSE):**

$$\text{MSE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2$$

- **Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE):**

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\text{MSE}}$$

- **R-squared (R^2):**

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \hat{y}_i)^2}{\sum_{i=1}^n (y_i - \bar{y})^2}$$

- **Mean Absolute Error (MAE):**

$$\text{MAE} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n |y_i - \hat{y}_i|$$

Source: Summarised from Hastie et al. (2009)

8 References

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